

Spectra of partially and fully rehydrated Synthetic Sodium A-Zeolite containing Nickel(II) ions

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Five samples of synthetic sodium A-zeolite containing 1.0, 2.4, 3.15, 3.9, and 4.6, Ni^{II} ions per unit cell were prepared by ion exchange method and characterised. The fully hydrated zeolites showed an octahedral structure of Ni^{II} ion. All five samples were dehydrated in vacuum at 620 K and their diffuse reflectance spectra at various stages of rehydration in contact with water vapour recorded. The visual and spectroscopic observations showed the reversible dehydration and rehydration of only Ni_{1.0}A zeolite. After long periods of rehydration, the fully rehydrated samples (greenish) of Ni_{2.4}A, Ni_{3.15}A and Ni_{3.9}A showed band maxima at 23 750 (± 50) cm⁻¹. The fully rehydrated sample (yellowish) of Ni_{4.6}A showed band maximum at 23 500 cm⁻¹. Surface area measurements indicated the structure collapse of only Ni_{4.6}A during evacuation above room temperature. In general, the rate sequence of rehydration of samples investigated, decreases as the Ni^{II} ion in the framework increases.

NICKEL exchanged zeolites form the basis of potentially valuable catalytic systems¹⁻³. The structural studies of Ni A-zeolites using reflectance spectroscopy^{4,5} and X-ray diffraction techniques have already been reported⁶. Interest in the use of zeolites containing transition metal ions in studies of surface phenomena continues to grow along with their applications in catalysis. Consequently, it is important that the siting of the cations, and their coordination state, behaviour during thermal treatment and interaction with sorbed molecules be well understood.

The aim of this paper is to report the results of spectroscopic studies using the diffuse reflectance technique on the effect of rehydration on the coordination and migration of Ni^{II} ion in type A-zeolite. As far as the authors are aware no similar type of work has yet been published.

Experimental

The starting material was synthetic Na A-zeolite (lot no. 4941040757) in the powder form, supplied by the Linde Division of the Union Carbide Corporation. Before use, the powder was stored in a desiccator over saturated calcium nitrate solution for several days for complete hydration.

Ion-exchange : Five samples of Ni Na-A-zeolites containing 1.0, 2.4, 3.15, 3.9 and 4.6 Ni^{II} ions per unit cell were prepared by ion-exchange methods. The procedure, used was similar as has been previously reported^{7,8}. NiCl₂.6H₂O (B.D.H.) was used

for introducing Ni^{II} ions in to type A-zeolite. The extent of ion-exchange was governed by the concentration of the nickel chloride solution, contact time and solution temperature. All five hydrated samples of zeolites were of green colour.

Methods : The stabilities of the structures of nickel exchanged A-zeolites were checked by X-ray diffraction and low temperature adsorption of krypton, which showed no loss of structure resulting from the exchanged process and during evacuation at high temperature. The number of water molecules per unit cell of the fully hydrated samples were determined by gravimetric measurements which were performed in a vacuum apparatus (sensitivity 1 mm=4.411 mg) with a trap cooled to 77 K situated close to the balance case. The chemical analysis and gravimetric studies of the samples of Ni A-zeolites were consistent with the following unit cell formulas : Ni_{1.0}A : 1Ni²⁺, 10Na⁺, [(AlO₂)₁₂(SiO₂)₁₂]¹²⁻, 32 H₂O ; Ni_{2.4}A : 2.4Ni²⁺, 7.2Na⁺, [(AlO₂)₁₂(SiO₂)₁₂]¹²⁻, 34 H₂O ; Ni_{3.15}A : 3.15Ni²⁺, 5.7Na⁺, [(AlO₂)₁₂(SiO₂)₁₂]¹²⁻, 39.3 H₂O ; Ni_{3.9}A : 3.9Ni²⁺, 4.2Na⁺, [(AlO₂)₁₂(SiO₂)₁₂]¹²⁻, 45.3 H₂O ; Ni_{4.6}A : 4.6Ni²⁺, 2.8Na⁺, [(AlO₂)₁₂(SiO₂)₁₂]¹²⁻, 47.8 H₂O.

For taking the diffuse reflectance spectra of the samples, the powdered zeolite specimens were compacted at a pressure of 2 285 kg/sq. cm in a 13 mm diameter die. The reflectance spectra were recorded at room temperature on Pye Unicam SP800 uv/visible spectrophotometer using a SP 890 diffuse reflectance accessory. The disc of the zeolite sample

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contained in a special evacuable pyrex cell having an optical window. The reference standard for all spectra was hydrated synthetic sodium type A-zeolite powder and the range employed was 11 500–32 500 cm^{-1} .

Results

The monolayer equivalent surface areas of dehydrated samples determined by adsorption of krypton at 77 K of $\text{Ni}_{1.0}\text{A}$, $\text{Ni}_{2.4}\text{A}$, $\text{Ni}_{3.15}\text{A}$, $\text{Ni}_{3.9}\text{A}$ and $\text{Ni}_{4.6}\text{A}$ were 27, 338, 306, 278 and 39 m^2g^{-1} , respectively. Diffuse reflectance spectra of the fully hydrated zeolites are shown in Fig. 1. The partially rehydrated reflectance spectra of $\text{Ni}_{1.0}\text{A}$, $\text{Ni}_{2.4}\text{A}$ and $\text{Ni}_{3.15}\text{A}$ after exposing the dehydrated samples to water vapour (air) for 10 min showed band maxima at 23 300, 21 500 and $\sim 23\,000$ cm^{-1} , respectively. For example, the spectra of $\text{Ni}_{2.4}\text{A}$ after exposing the dehydrated sample to water vapour for 10 min and 6 weeks are shown in Fig. 2 by curves 1 and 2, respectively. All five samples of partially rehydrated Ni A-zeolites were kept in a desiccator over calcium nitrate solution at room temperature for several weeks for complete rehydration. The reflectance spectrum of fully rehydrated $\text{Ni}_{1.0}\text{A}$ is identical to its fully hydrated spectrum (Fig. 1, curve 1). The reflectance spectra of $\text{Ni}_{2.4}\text{A}$, $\text{Ni}_{3.15}\text{A}$ and $\text{Ni}_{3.9}\text{A}$ after 6, 7 and 9 weeks complete rehydration showed band maxima at $\sim 23\,750$ (± 50) cm^{-1} .

Fig. 1. Reflectance spectra of hydrated Ni A-zeolite: (1) $\text{Ni}_{1.0}\text{A}$, (2) $\text{Ni}_{2.4}\text{A}$, (3) $\text{Ni}_{3.15}\text{A}$, (4) $\text{Ni}_{3.9}\text{A}$ and (5) $\text{Ni}_{4.6}\text{A}$.

The fully rehydrated spectrum of $\text{Ni}_{2.4}\text{A}$ is shown by curve 2 in Fig. 2. The curves 4 and 3 in Fig. 2 show respectively the fully rehydrated spectra of $\text{Ni}_{3.15}\text{A}$ and $\text{Ni}_{3.9}\text{A}$. The fully rehydrated samples of Ni A-zeolites investigated were greenish in colour except $\text{Ni}_{4.6}\text{A}$ which was kept in a desiccator over

Fig. 2. Diffuse reflectance spectra of rehydrated Ni A-zeolite: (1) $\text{Ni}_{2.4}\text{A}$ exposed to water vapour for 10 min, (2) $\text{Ni}_{2.4}\text{A}$ exposed to water vapour for 6 weeks, (3) $\text{Ni}_{3.9}\text{A}$ exposed to water vapour for 7 weeks and (4) $\text{Ni}_{3.15}\text{A}$ exposed to water vapour for 9 weeks.

calcium nitrate solution for complete rehydration for 14 weeks. The colour of rehydrated $\text{Ni}_{4.6}\text{A}$ after 3 or 14 weeks was yellowish and showed band maximum at 23 500 cm^{-1} .

Discussion

The reflectance spectra of fully hydrated Ni A-zeolites are shown in Fig. 1, only for comparison, and have been discussed elsewhere⁹. Spectrum 1 in Fig. 2 resembles the spectrum recorded after outgassing $\text{Ni}_{2.4}\text{A}$ in vacuum (*ca.* 10^{-6} torr) at 340 K, where mainly quasi-octahedral structures, $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{Ox})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3$ were reported¹⁰. There is general agreement^{4,5,11} that in the fully hydrated Ni A-zeolite, the Ni^{II} ion is octahedrally coordinated to six water molecules, $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$. The spectrum 2 (completely rehydrated) in Fig. 2 nearly matches with its fully hydrated spectrum (Fig. 1, curve 2) except in this case the band maximum at $\sim 26\,100$ cm^{-1} has diminished, but it shows rather a weak band at $\sim 23\,750$ cm^{-1} . The bands at $\sim 13\,800$ and $\sim 15\,700$ cm^{-1} which were recorded in the hydrated sample are also very weak in curve 2 of Fig. 2. The curves 4 and 3 of Fig. 2 do not resemble their fully hydrated spectra (Fig. 1) because here the band maxima of $\text{Ni}_{3.15}\text{A}$ and $\text{Ni}_{3.9}\text{A}$ at 26 500 and 26 600 cm^{-1} (which were recorded in the hydrated samples), respectively, have not emerged. The rehydrated spectra of $\text{Ni}_{3.15}\text{A}$ and $\text{Ni}_{3.9}\text{A}$ show band maxima rather at $\sim 23\,750$ cm^{-1} . The bands at $\sim 14\,000$ and $\sim 15\,700$ cm^{-1} of curves 4 and 3 respectively in Fig. 2 of rehydrated spectra are also very weak.

The monoequivalent surface area measurements by the adsorption of krypton at 77 K of $\text{Ni}_{2.4}\text{A}$, (338 m^2g^{-1}), $\text{Ni}_{3.15}\text{A}$ (306 m^2g^{-1}) and $\text{Ni}_{3.9}\text{A}$ (278 m^2g^{-1}) confirmed the integrity of their structures during dehydration in vacuum up to 620 K. The surface areas of Ni A-zeolites have been already discussed¹⁰. The low surface area of $\text{Ni}_{1.0}\text{A}$ (27 m^2g^{-1}) is due to the partial blockage of the 8-rings by Na^+ ions. It has been previously reported by Klier and Ralek^{4,5} that in dehydrated Ni A-zeolites the Ni^{II} ions are trigonally coordinated with three zeolitic oxygens in the 6-rings. Moreover, it has been indicated⁶ by X-ray diffraction study that in hydrated $\text{Ni}_{2.5}\text{A}$ -zeolite, one Ni^{II} ion is located in the center of the sodalite unit where it is fully aquated. Thus, it is suggested that during rehydration, in the cases of $\text{Ni}_{2.4}\text{A}$, $\text{Ni}_{3.15}\text{A}$ and $\text{Ni}_{3.9}\text{A}$ more than one Ni^{II} ion may enter in sodalite unit or beta cavity (6.6 Å in diameter) where due to less space all Ni^{II} ions are unable to reform the hexaquo-complexes, $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$ (*ca.* 4.78 Å in diameter). This suggestion is also supported from the colour noted and the spectra (Fig. 2) of the rehydrated samples.

As far as $\text{Ni}_{4.6}\text{A}$ (76.6% exchanged) is concerned, the surface area (39 m^2g^{-1}) measurement indicated its framework disintegration during evacuation above room temperature (298–400 K). The structure

collapse of such highly exchanged Ni A-zeolite ($\text{Ni}_{4.6}\text{A}$) has already been reported by Dyer and Wilkinson¹². The spectrum recorded after exposing the dehydrated $\text{Ni}_{4.6}\text{A}$ to water vapour for rehydration for 5 min was similar to its dehydrated spectrum¹⁰. The partially rehydrated $\text{Ni}_{4.6}\text{A}$ could not regain its original bright green colour even after keeping for 14 weeks in a constant humidity desiccator over saturated calcium nitrate solution at room temperature, which shows no reformation of any $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$ complex. The colour of rehydrated $\text{Ni}_{4.6}\text{A}$ after 3 or 4 weeks exposure to water vapour remained the same, *i.e.* yellowish. However, the spectra of rehydrated $\text{Ni}_{4.6}\text{A}$ has shown that some time dependent rehydration occurred. In general, the visual observations of changes in colour and reflectance spectra of rehydrated samples indicated that the rate sequence of rehydration was as $\text{Ni}_1\text{A} > \text{Ni}_{2.4}\text{A} > \text{Ni}_{3.15}\text{A} > \text{Ni}_{3.9}\text{A} > \text{Ni}_{4.6}\text{A}$. The high rate of rehydration shown by low exchanged zeolites is attributed to the relocation of the maximum number of Ni^{II} ions to their original sites and reformation of hexaquo $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$ ions in the zeolite framework.

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